
GLOBAL-SCALE MODELLING OF MOUNTAIN GLACIER EVOLUTION SINCE THE LAST INTERGLACIAL

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ABSTRACT

Mountain glacier evolution since the last interglacial remains poorly constrained, with limited spatial and temporal coverage. Traditional approaches typically target major climatic events or operate at coarse spatial resolution or over limited spatial domains. Here we address these limitations by applying the AI-based Instructed Glacier Model (IGM), a deep-learning ice-flow emulator enabling efficient GPU-accelerated transient simulations, to reconstruct mountain glacier evolution since ~ 130 ka at 500 m resolution across eight broad mountain ranges in North America, South America, Eurasia, and Africa. We perform 617 parameter-calibration experiments varying paleoclimate and ice-dynamic parameters, with an average runtime of 21 hours per experiment. Model performance is assessed using combined areal and volumetric validation, and we introduce a reproducible probabilistic model-evaluation framework combining confusion-matrix metrics, critical success index scores, and simulation ranking to identify ensembles of acceptable model configurations rather than a single best-fit solution. Our results show that IGM can reproduce realistic ice-flow patterns, glacier geometries, and transient evolution across full glacial–interglacial cycles, demonstrating that machine-learning models on ice dynamics generalise to regions and conditions outside the original training domain, although performance declines at coarser spatial resolutions. Our probability-based model evaluation reveals areas of robust agreement of glaciated pixels. We identify areas sensitive to parameter variation, providing new way to visualise spatial uncertainty and ice–climate interactions. Together, these results demonstrate the feasibility of global-scale, high-resolution, transient glacier modelling over orbital timescales using a deep-learning-informed model, and establish a transparent

methodology for paleoglacier model evaluation that is equifinality-aware, and explicitly incorporates validation and calibration uncertainties.

Keywords glacier-modelling · paleoclimate · mountain-glacier

1 Introduction

Most major mountain ranges around the world are known to have been glaciated during the Late Pleistocene [Thackray et al., 2008, Hughes and Gibbard, 2018, Ehlers et al., 2011, Lima et al., (in rev)]. However, glacial evolution for many mountain ranges is unknown through large parts of the Last Glacial Cycle (LGC; ~ 120 to $\sim 11,7$ ka) and the Holocene ($\sim 11,7$ ka to today). Although numerous paleoglacier reconstructions have been conducted using geomorphic [e.g. Clapperton, 1983, Osmaston, 2004, Gillespie and Zehfuss, 2004, Gobejishvili et al., 2011, Groos et al., 2021, Delmas et al., 2022] and numerical models [e.g. Kessler et al., 2006, Kull et al., 2008, Stansell et al., 2022, Doughty et al., 2023, Leger et al., 2025], these studies have often reconstructed steady-state conditions or performed transient simulations centred on major climatic events such as the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM; 26.5–19 ka) and the Younger Dryas (12.9–11.7 ka).

While some mountain ranges have been the focus of transient simulations of glacier evolution spanning glacial-interglacial cycles [e.g. Becker et al., 2017, Seguinot et al., 2018, Yan et al., 2021, 2023, Juvet and Cordonnier, 2023], these simulations are generally performed at spatial resolutions >1 km. Such simulations are essential not only for understanding mountain glacier responses to climate changes, but also for interdisciplinary alpine research, including studies of sediment flux, lake development, and the timing and pathways of vegetation dynamics [Sternai et al., 2013, Kaufmann and Romanov, 2012, Flantua et al., 2019, Hurtado and Gallen, 2025]. Others have demonstrated that transient simulations through glacial-interglacial cycles can be performed at finer spatial resolutions (< 1 km) [e.g. Xu et al., 2014, Žebre et al., 2021, O’Donnell, 2010], but typically at the cost of limiting the simulation domain to smaller catchments. High-resolution glacier evolution models further reduce model–data differences and improve the representation of glacier–landscape interactions. Therefore, simulations spanning full glacial–interglacial cycles remain constrained by a trade-off between spatial resolution and spatial coverage.

This trade-off is due the computational costs and runtime demands of conventional numerical modelling approaches (e.g. Parallel Ice Sheet Model (PISM), iSOSIA) that have hitherto made it unfeasible to simulate entire mountain ranges at finer spatial resolution over full glacial-interglacial cycles. However, these computational limitations are now being overcome by the state-of-the-art AI-based Instructed Glacier Model (IGM; Juvet et al. 2022, Juvet), a machine-learning driven glacier modelling framework in which ice-flow dynamics are emulated using deep learning. Whereas conventional glacier models rely on central processing unit (CPU) based solvers that numerically compute ice-flow physics at every time step, IGM delivers a pre-trained, physically instructed deep-learning-based emulator, replacing the computationally expensive CPU-based with graphics processing units (GPU) accelerated inference [Juvet et al., 2022]. In other words, IGM enables parallelisation of calculations, resulting in substantially faster simulation outputs at a fraction of the computational cost [Juvet et al., 2022].

Previous IGM-based studies reported reductions in glacier simulation runtime of one to three orders of magnitude relative to conventional CPU-based models [Juvet et al., 2022, Juvet and Cordonnier, 2023, Cook et al., 2023, Leger et al., 2025], overcoming not only the computational bottleneck of transient, high-resolution glacier modelling, but also enabling extensive model parametrisation and sensitivity testing. The systematic exploration of key glacier–climate parameters is essential for quantifying uncertainty, assessing model robustness, and addressing equifinality in transient glacier simulations (i.e., where multiple parameter combinations can yield similarly plausible glacier geometries), all of which are required to accurately represent complex topographies, ice dynamics, and paleoclimates.

Despite these advances, important limitations remain in improving model-data agreement, including:

1. model initialisation and forcing, such as initial ice geometry, model spin-up, and the application of climate forcing;
2. limited temporal resolution and uneven spatial coverage of paleo-proxy records for paleoclimate reconstructions;
3. simplified or poorly constrained process parametrisations in glacier models (e.g., basal sliding, ice flow behaviour) for most mountain regions;
4. limited availability and uneven spatial distribution of well-dated, geomorphically based validation data with sufficient spatial accuracy for direct comparison with model outputs; and
5. absence of standardised validation workflows and performance metrics in glacier modelling studies, which make model evaluation under equifinality largely dependent on qualitative visual judgment.

In this study, we address these limitations through a combination of established best practices and novel methodological developments that combine long-term transient simulations, regionally informed climate forcing, systematic parameter calibration, spatially explicit validation data, and equifinality-aware model evaluation. We apply the IGM v2.2.3 to model transient glacier evolution over the past 130,000 years at 500 m spatial resolution across 14 simulation domains, covering eight mountain ranges (Fig. 1). Our approach incorporates proxy and model-based paleoclimate reconstructions to regionally scale climate forcing, and explores model uncertainty through 617 parameter-calibration experiments across all mountain ranges. Our study overcomes steady-state reconstructions and snapshot simulations, resolution constraints, spatial extent limitations, while allowing the test of different parameters for paleoclimate and ice dynamics, and enabling a systematic assessment of the applicability of IGM across diverse glaciological and climatic settings.

Further, we propose a statistically, spatially explicit, and equifinality-aware validation workflow and performance metric, rather than qualitative visual comparison. First, model–data differences are evaluated by quantifying areal spatial concordance between model output and geomorphic glacier reconstructions, rather than distance from glacial landforms. Second, our performance metrics explicitly account for equifinality by characterising a probabilistic range of plausible glacier configurations supported by multiple acceptable model simulations, rather than subjectively selecting a single best simulation. Together, this validation framework overcomes reliance on qualitative visual judgement and subjective best-fit selection under equifinality, enabling transparent and reproducible model–data evaluation.

Thus, this work applies IGM to perform a three-dimensional mass balance-ice dynamics transient glacier simulation since the last interglacial (~130 ka), producing reconstructions of glacier extent, ice thickness, and surface velocity. We perform up to 108 parameter-calibration experiments for each simulation domain, incorporated regionally informed paleoclimate inferences to scale climate forcing, and introduce a quantitative, spatial validation framework that explicitly accounts for equifinality. Beyond producing transient glacier evolution simulations at an unprecedented combination of spatial extent, orbital timescale and high-resolution, this study introduces quantitative, equifinality-aware validation framework for glacier models and provides a benchmark evaluation of IGM’s ability to deliver high-quality glacier reconstructions across global mountain ranges.

2 Methods

This section describes (1) the selection process for the chosen study areas (i.e. mountain ranges and simulation domains) in Sect. 2.1; (2) the data preparation of the digital elevation model in Sect. 2.2; (3) the climate forcing datasets and their incorporation into the model in Sect. 2.3; (4) the setup and calibration for the coupled mass balance-ice dynamics glacier model in Sect. 2.4; (5) the model validation workflow in Sect. 2.5; and the model evaluation framework in Sect 2.6.

2.1 Study areas

The selection of mountain ranges is based on (a) geographic distribution of the mountain ranges around the globe, as we investigate the applicability of the IGM on different topographic and climate settings, (b) the availability of climate forcing data, i.e. temperature and precipitation paleoreconstructions, and (c) the existence of validation datasets for the LGM modelled outputs. To reduce the complexity of the simulations, we excluded regions with marine-terminating glaciers (e.g. New Zealand), as sea-ice interactions is currently a limitation of the IGM.

We select 8 mountain ranges in North America, South America, Africa and Eurasia based on the global inventory of mountain ranges published by Global Mountain Biodiversity Assessment (hierarchical levels 3-5) Snethlage et al. [2021, 2022]. We further subdivide these into 14 distinct simulation domains (Fig. 1). Our simulation domains consist of (1) Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta, (2) Cordillera Oriental and Cordillera de Merida, (3) Cordillera Central and Cordillera Occidental (Colombia), and (4) Cordillera Real and Cordillera Occidental (Ecuador) in the Northern Andes. The Ethiopian Highlands are subdivided as (5) Semien Mountains, (6) Bale Mountains, and (7) Arsi Mountains. In the Eastern Rift Mountains, (8) Mount Elgon, and (9) Mount Kenya and Mount Kilimanjaro compose the simulation domains. Finally, the (10) Ruwenzori mountains, (11) Sierra Nevada, (12) Greater Caucasus, (13) Pyrenees and (14) European Alps as individual simulation domains.

Subdivision of mountain ranges into multiple simulation domains is necessary because climatic forcing and ice-dynamic parameters vary heterogeneously within a given range. It is also required for computational reasons, as some ranges accumulate large ice volumes over extensive areas that exceed the capacity of a local computer for parameter testing.

Figure 1: Selected mountain ranges and simulation areas for glacier evolution simulations. The selected mountain ranges are shown in coloured polygons, respective caption in bigger font size. The simulation areas are shown in coloured dashed lines, respective caption in smaller font size. When mountain ranges and simulation areas are referred by the same nomenclature, only one caption is provided. Simulation areas range from $\sim 8,000$ to $300,000$ km^2 . Mountain ranges by Snelhage et al. [2021, 2022] at different hierarchical levels 3-5. Basemap powered by ESRI, GEBCO, Garmin, NaturalVue in ArcGIS Pro 3.2.2 (2023).

2.2 Digital Elevation Model

Global terrain models generally only provided bedrock elevations under the surface of the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets, thus including ice-cover of mountain glacier. Then, to create a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with ice-free topography, we remove the present-day ice thickness, acquired from the Farinotti et al. [2019] dataset, from the GEBCO 2025 global terrain model [GEBCO Bathymetric Compilation Group 2025, 2025]. First, the present-day ice thickness dataset is downscaled to match the 15-Arcsec resolution of GEBCO 2025. Second, the present-day ice thickness is subtracted from the global terrain model. Finally, an ice-free DEM at 500 m resolution is generated.

2.3 Paleoclimate forcing

2.3.1 Temperature

The near-surface air temperature is obtained from the CHELSA-climatologies V2.1 dataset [Karger et al., 2017, 2025], a global 1 km dataset representing the 1981–2010 climatological reference period. Mean monthly temperatures from CHELSA is adjusted to paleoclimatic conditions using temperature anomalies (ΔT) reconstructed from the EPICA Dome C ice core [Jouzel et al., 2007]. For each region, ΔT_{epica} is further scaled to account for polar amplification effects. Following this approach, temperature is calculated as:

$$T(x, y, t) = T_{\text{obs}} + \Delta T_{\text{epica}} \cdot f_{\text{regional}} \quad (1)$$

where T_{obs} is the monthly mean observed temperature (CHELSA-climatologies V2.1 dataset), ΔT is the EPICA Dome C temperature anomaly, and f_{regional} is the regional scaling factor to scale EPICA DOME C temperature anomaly to regional temperature anomalies (see section 2.3.2).

2.3.2 Regional scaling factor

The polar amplification factor (PAF) is a quantitative measure of how much the polar regions (ΔT_{polar} , i.e., Antarctic or Arctic) warm or cool compared to the global mean temperature change (ΔT_{global}) (Equation 2). In the context of paleoclimate reconstructions for the LGM, typical values from the literature place the Antarctic amplification factor at approximately one to two times the global cooling [Masson-Delmotte et al., 2006, Hansen et al., 2013], whereas the Arctic amplification factor is estimated as two to four times the global temperature cooling [Masson-Delmotte et al., 2006, Xie et al., 2022].

$$\text{PAF} = \Delta T_{\text{polar}} / \Delta T_{\text{global}} \quad (2)$$

In paleoclimate and paleoglacier studies, the PAF is often used to scale global temperature estimates to polar temperature changes, to compare model versus proxy reconstructions of past climates, and to derive input temperatures for glacier or ice-sheet models [Rentier et al., 2025, Seguinot et al., 2018]). In this study, we use Antarctic mean temperature changes ($\Delta T_{\text{Antarctic}}$) together with regional mean LGM temperature changes ($\Delta T_{\text{regional}}$) to derive regional scaling factors (f_{regional}) for each mountain range (Equation 3). This procedure scales $\Delta T_{\text{Antarctic}}$ to $\Delta T_{\text{regional}}$ at the LGM and enables estimation of regional LGM temperature cooling from CHELSA average monthly temperatures [See Karger et al., 2017, Equation 1]

$$f_{\text{regional}} = \Delta T_{\text{regional}} / \Delta T_{\text{Antarctic}} \quad (3)$$

The value of $\Delta T_{\text{Antarctic}}$ is calculated using 100-year means of the EPICA Dome C ice-core record [Jouzel et al., 2007] for the interval 26.5–19 ka (i.e., -9.47 °C), representing the LGM period [Clark et al., 2009]. To calculate $\Delta T_{\text{regional}}$, we performed a literature review of paleoclimate reconstruction studies at the LGM, both proxy-based and model-based across all selected mountain ranges of this study. The compiled $\Delta T_{\text{regional}}$ values are grouped by mountain range (Table 1) and averaged to derive a representative $\Delta T_{\text{regional}}$ for each range. The bibliography of the literature review, the corresponding data, and the calculation script are provided in the Supplementary File S1: Regional Scaling Factors.

We reviewed a total of 82 paleoclimate reconstructions. As the distribution of reconstructions is uneven across mountain ranges, we initially adopted the global scaling factor (f_{global}), defined as 0.5 [Hansen et al., 2013], for mountain ranges with fewer than 10 paleoclimate reconstructions. Additional calibration is performed in f_{regional} , as the $\Delta T_{\text{Antarctic}}$ does not uniformly and globally represents regional LGM cooling due to local and regional atmospheric circulation, orographic effects, and differing proxy sensitivities (see more in section 2.4.5).

2.3.3 Temperature lapse s

The lapse rate is the vertical temperature gradient in the atmosphere, which is calculated using:

$$LR = \Delta T_{\text{present}} / \Delta Z \quad (4)$$

Table 1: Climate proxy records and regional scaling factors summary.

Mountain region	Proxy records #	Initial f_{regional}	Temperature cooling ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
European Alps	19	1.19	11.30
Pyrenees	19	1.19	11.30
Ruwenzori Mountains	18	0.47	4.46
Eastern Rift Mountains	22	0.44	4.17
Ethiopian Highlands	9	0.50	4.75
Greater Caucasus	3	0.50	4.75
Northern Andes	8	0.50	4.75
Sierra Nevada	3	0.50	4.75

where LR is the lapse rate, $\Delta T_{\text{present}}$ the present-day vertical difference in temperature and ΔZ the change in elevation. The calculation is performed on a global set of these two values using a 3x3 pixel window (30 Arcsec pixel resolution) following the approach proposed by Wang et al. [2024]. Present-day temperature data are obtained from CHELSA-BIOCLIM+ (Bioclimatic factor 01; Mean annual temperature) [Brun et al., 2022] and elevation data from the GEBCO [GEBCO Bathymetric Compilation Group 2025, 2025]. The calculated lapse rates are cleaned following Tukey’s method (1977) of using 1.5 times the interquartile range as a threshold for outliers. For each mountain range, the lapse rate values are averaged over the bounding box belonging to the specific mountain range (See Fig. 1 for the bounding boxes). This results in a unique lapse rate value (K m^{-1}) for each mountain range used as a constant value throughout the simulation. To circumvent the discrepancy between the CHELSA temperature (temperature at the present day glacier elevation) and the modelled ice elevation, the location-specific mean lapse rate is multiplied by the ice elevation minus the CHELSA elevation at each time step in the simulation.

2.3.4 Precipitation

We obtain the mean monthly precipitation from the CHELSA-climatologies V2.1 dataset [Karger et al., 2017, 2025]. We adjust the paleoprecipitation using the glacial index scheme [e.g. Niu et al., 2019, Greve et al., 1999, Tarasov and Peltier, 2004, Jouvet et al., 2023, Leger et al., 2025], in which a transient climate forcing is derived from a reference paleoclimate record (the index) and applied to a modern climatological baseline using time-varying anomalies.

To this end, a normalised glacial index time series $G(t)$ is defined using the EPICA Dome C ice core ΔT , as our reference paleoclimate record. The coldest EPICA ΔT (i.e. -10.58, 24.015 ka BP) during our simulation period is assigned $G = 0$, while the present-day reference climate (i.e., CHELSA dataset) is assigned $G = 1$:

$$G(t) = \frac{\Delta T(t) - \Delta T_{LGM}}{\Delta T_{PD} - \Delta T_{LGM}} \quad (5)$$

Intermediate values of $G(t)$ therefore describe the relative position between colder and warmer conditions through time, as:

$$P(x, y, t) = P_{\text{obs}}(G + P_{LGM}(1 - G)) \quad (6)$$

where P is the model precipitation ($\text{kg m}^2 \text{a}^{-1}$), P_{obs} is the observed monthly mean precipitation ($\text{kg m}^2 \text{a}^{-1}$) from the CHELSA dataset [Karger et al., 2017, 2025], G is the glacial index, and P_{LGM} is the precipitation scaling factor that represents the relative change in precipitation at the coldest EPICA ΔT conditions. The P_{LGM} controls the magnitude of precipitation reduction or enhancement at glacial conditions and is applied progressively through time according to the glacial index. Precipitation scaling is specified individually for each simulation domain (see section 2.4.5).

2.4 Glacier model

2.4.1 Resources

We run IGM using both a local desktop machine with NVIDIA GeForce RTX 5080, and the high-performance computing system Saga, provided by Norwegian infrastructure Sigma2. Saga has 16 nodes with GPU’s that are used in parallel. There are 8 nodes with the NVIDIA P100 (16 GiB RAM) GPU and 8 nodes with NVIDIA A100 (80 GiB RAM). The NVIDIA P100 model is sufficiently powerful to run IGM at 500 m in most of our simulation domains, allowing multiple simulations in parallel on the same node. However, the European Alps is modelled with the NVIDIA A100 GPU model, as the extent area of its simulation domain and the build-up ice requires more than 16 GiB of RAM. In contrast, the smaller locations (e.g. Ruwenzori, Mount Kenya, and Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta) are fully modelled with the local GPU. Processing runtime varies from 2.98 hours at Bale Mountains (Ethiopian Highlands) to 101.73 hours at Eastern

Cordillera and Merida Cordillera (Northern Andes). Averaged processing time per simulation domain can be seen in Table 5.

2.4.2 Model initialisation

Simulations are initialised with a 10 kyr spin up over ice-free present-day bedrock. The spin up period is forced with a constant climate forcing, where temperature and precipitation correspond to the model year 130 ka. The purpose of the spin up is to simulate an interglacial state by overriding the ΔT_{epica} time series. This allows the model to reach a dynamically stable state before the start of the period of interest.

Glacier modelling is done at spatial resolution of 500 m, with 16 vertical layers. Climate forcing data is downscaled to match model resolution. Time steps are set to 1 year, including the Surface Mass Balance (SMB) calculations. At every 100 time step, ice thickness, volume, and flow components are saved.

Table 2: Glacier model input parameters. Ranges indicate regional variation across simulation domains.

Name	Value	Unit
Ice deformation		
Ice density	910	kg m^{-3}
Gravitational acceleration	9.81	m s^{-2}
Arrhenius factor	78.0	–
Enhancement factor	1	–
Glen’s flow law exponent	3	–
Regularisation parameter (Glen)	1×10^{-5}	–
Number of vertical layers	10	–
Vertical spacing (denser near bed)	graded	–
Basal sliding		
Sliding coefficient	0.01 – 0.18	$\text{MPa yr}^m \text{ m}^{-m}$
Weertman’s sliding law exponent	3	–
Regularisation parameter (sliding)	1×10^{-10}	–
Mass balance		
Degree-day factor (snow)	-0.0065	$\text{m yr}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
Degree-day factor (ice)	1.387	$\text{m yr}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
de	0.9 – 1.6	–
Solid precipitation threshold	0.0	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Liquid precipitation threshold	2.0	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Refreezing factor	0.6	–
Density of water	1000	kg m^{-3}
Density of ice	910	kg m^{-3}
Maximum accumulation rate	6	m yr^{-1}
Hydrological year shift	0.75	–
Climate forcing		
Temperature scaling factor	0.40 – 1.19	–
Precipitation scaling factor	0.1 – 1.5	–
Lapse rate (regional mean)	-6.622 to -4.431	K km^{-1}

2.4.3 The Instructed Glacier Model

In this study, we include the IGM modules for ice flow, vertical flow, ice thickness and avalanche simulation. We use IGM’s default values for the input parameters in these modules (Table 2). For climate forcing and Surface Mass Balance (SMB) calculations, custom modules are required to adapt to the input parameters of the paleo-time scale. To shorten computation cost and calibration time modules for enthalpy, particles and isostatic adjustment are not included.

The Instructed Glacier Model (IGM) is a deep learning glacier evolution model that speeds up simulation by approximating the flow equations with a physics-informed deep learning emulator [Leger et al., 2025]. The emulator is pre-trained on a variety of glacier settings, and continues frequent re-training to a novel flow-regime during simulation [Leger et al., 2025]. Physical laws and relationships inform the training of emulator. Glen’s flow law [Glen, 1955, Nye, 1953] is used to solve the stress and strain associated with ice deformation. The model uses the Blatter–Pattyn approximation for ice dynamics [Hutter, 1983, Schoof and Hewitt, 2013], rather than solving the full Stokes equations [Jouvet and Cordonnier, 2023]. At the lower boundary, sliding and basal shear stress is solved with the non-linear Weertman friction

Table 3: Summary of varied parameters and their meaning in the simulations ensemble.

Varying Model Parameter	Model Component	Min	Max	Description
Regional scaling factor	Climate forcing	0.2	1.1	Glacial Index Method input precipitation at LGM compared to present day.
Precipitation factor at LGM	Climate forcing	0.1	2.1	
Sliding Coefficient	Sliding component	0.01	0.45	Positive Degree Day melt rate factor for ice
Melt rate factor ice	Surface Mass Balance	0.8	1.9	
Melt rate factor snow	Surface Mass Balance	0.8	1.9	

relationship [Jouvet and Cordonnier, 2023]. The snow distribution on the surface of a glacier that occur in the form of avalanches or by wind transportation, is included with IGM avalanche model default parameters.

2.4.4 Surface Mass Balance

We use a positive degree-day (PDD) model to calculate the SMB, adapted from Leger et al. [2025]. In a PDD model, accumulation happens when precipitation falls as snow, typically when temperature is below 0°C, and ablation occurs when temperatures are higher than 0°C. In our PDD mode, we apply a linear snow-rain precipitation transition from 0°C to 2°C, where snow-precipitation dominates when temperature is below 0°C and rain-precipitation dominates when temperature is higher than 2°C.

We calculate PDD based on Calov and Greve [2005] and Hock [2003] equations, in which our temperature inputs (Sect. 2.3.1) is corrected by the lapse rate (Sect. 2.3.3), and precipitation is normalised by a glacial index time series (2.3.4). Additionally, we apply degree-day melt factors (DDF) for snow and ice, which varies according a common degree-day scaling factor in the parameter calibration (Sect. 2.4.5), and a fixed refreeze factor at 60%.

2.4.5 Parameter calibration

We create parameter-calibration experiments for each mountain region based on a combination of regional climatic settings and ice dynamics. We vary four key parameters through parameter-calibration experiments: temperature, precipitation, degree-day scaling factor and sliding coefficient (Table 3). A minimum of 27 parameter-calibration experiments are simulated per mountain region, which may increase if a given mountain range requires more climate-ice dynamics parameter combinations for optimal results. This set of parameter-calibration experiments per mountain range is addressed as a simulation ensemble.

Before the simulation ensemble is started, a larger range of parameters is tested with 1 km resolution in a 10 kyr period up to the LGM. In this pre-calibration step, the LGM time step is validated and ranked in the same way as the normal simulation ensemble (excluding the present-day time step validation). This gives each pre-calibration simulation a rank. As a tool to select the best parameter range for each value, the mean rank of the parameter values is measured. By iterating this process and/or testing multiple values, we can identify the values that give the highest rank per varied parameter, thereby providing an efficient method to approximate the best value ranges for each parameter before the simulation ensemble.

Temperature is calibrated only when precipitation, degree-day scaling factor and sliding coefficient calibration do not return realistic model outputs. It occurs when few paleoclimate proxies are available, or when the Antarctica-based scaling approach systematically over- or underestimated temperature (Sect. 2.3.2). If temperature calibration is required, f_{regional} is adjusted, rather than directly changing the temperature values. Therefore, f_{regional} calibration reflects structural uncertainty in both the polar reference record and the limited proxy constraints, ensuring physically consistent regional temperature forcing for glacier modelling.

Precipitation is varied by a scaling factor of Eq. 6, effectively setting a percentage of the present-day CHELSA precipitation (P_{LGM}) to the LGM time of the simulation. As both ice dynamics and SMB depend on several poorly-constrained parameters (most mountain ranges lack detailed reviews of these parameters), we test different sliding coefficient values and DDFs for snow and ice, where the latter vary by a common scaling factor. This combination reduces the complexity of the ensemble by lowering the total number of calibration simulations, while still allowing experiments with varying melt rates for both snow and ice.

By varying each parameter independently in the ensemble, we construct a partial factorial calibration set in which every parameter combination, except the temperature regional scaling factor, is evaluated (See Table 3 for a summary). Thus, the minimum 27 parameter-calibration experiments per simulation assemble is the result of three varying values for each parameter (P_{LGM} , sliding coefficient, and DDF). In the calibration stage, if ensembles show low validation scores or unrealistic ice build up in several simulations, more values are added to the relevant parameters and the ensemble is expanded.

2.5 Model validation

2.5.1 Validation datasets

We employ GLACIMONTIS geodatabase [Lima et al., in review] as the validation dataset for our LGM modelled outputs. GLACIMONTIS is a global geodatabase that integrates geomorphically-based reconstructions of maximum recorded areal extents of mountain glaciers during the MIS 3–2 (i.e., during the local LGM spanning 57–14 ka), compiled from 209 studies across 271 mountain ranges worldwide. In total, GLACIMONTIS compiles 15,007 individual mountain glacier geomorphic reconstructions, including 8,809 geomorphic reconstructions compiled for the first time in a global geodatabase. GLACIMONTIS provides a robust spatially distributed validation dataset for model evaluation, as it represents the most comprehensive and up-to-date geodatabase of mountain glacier areal extent at the global and local LGM.

To ensure comparability between GLACIMONTIS and our modelled outputs, we select from our simulations the glacier outlines corresponding to the maximum ice-extent area occurring between 57–14 ka. For each simulation domain, validation is performed against the corresponding published geomorphic glacier reconstructions compiled in GLACIMONTIS (Table 4).

Table 4: Geomorphically based glacier reconstructions used to validate simulation modelled outputs at the LGM

Mountain range	Source
Northern Andes	Clapperton, 1983; Stansell et al., 2007; Frenierre et al., 2011; Ceballos et al., 2012
Ethiopian Highlands	Umer et al., 2004; Gross et al., 2021
Eastern Rift Mountains	Osmaston, 2004
Rwenzori Mountains	Doughty et al., 2021
Sierra Nevada	Gillespie and Zehfuss, 2004; Walter, 2022
Greater Caucasus	Gobejishvili et al., 2011
Pyrenees	Delmas et al., 2022
European Alps	Buoncristiani and Campy, 2004; Schlüchter, 2004; Bini et al., 2004; Castiglioni, 2004; Carraro and Giardino, 2004; Van Husen, 2004; Fiebig et al., 2004; Bavec and Verbič, 2004; Burkhalter and Bini, 2009; Ferik et al., 2017; Schuster et al., 2020; Serra et al., 2022; Kamleitner et al., 2022; Rettig et al., 2023

For the present-day validation dataset, we employ the RGI 7.0 [RGI Consortium, 2023] and the global distribution of estimated ice thickness of glaciers [Farinotti et al., 2019]. The RGI 7.0 is a global inventory of contemporary glacier outlines derived from multiple data sources with a nominal inventory date centred around the year 2000, which we refer hereafter as model present-day. Accordingly, we extracted the simulated glacier outlines of the model present-day to validate against the RGI 7.0 dataset. The same approach is applied to the present-day validation dataset of glacier volume Farinotti et al. [2019], which is a consensus estimate for the ice thickness distribution of all glaciers on Earth derived from the RGI 6.0 [RGI Consortium, 2017]. This practice is consistent with other glacier-modelling studies that validate present-day glacier area and volume against RGI and RGI-derived benchmark datasets [Yan et al., 2018, Wijngaard et al., 2019, Yang et al., 2025, Bonsoms et al., 2025].

2.5.2 Ice extent validation

We use a confusion matrix approach to spatially compare the simulated areal extent outputs of each experimental setup at the LGM and present-day against the validation datasets. Before validation, a 5 m ice thickness minimum threshold is applied to the model output. Although confusion matrix approach is not yet commonly applied to paleoglacier modelled output validation [e.g. Depolli et al., 2024], it is often applied in the validation of spatial products [e.g. Robbins et al., 2024, Li et al., 2025].

To quantify spatial agreement (i.e., ice-cover fit and misfit) between the modelled and validation glacier extents, we classify our modelled outputs into glacier presence, glacier absence, glacier overestimation and glacier underestimation

Figure 2: Spatial application of the confusion-matrix to validate a glacier simulated area in the Ecuadorian Cordilleras (Northern Andes). In this schematic example, correct presence (CP), correct absence (CA), underestimation (U) and overestimation (O) are mapped by comparing the glacier simulated area to the geomorphic reconstructed glacier of Clapperton [1983], acquired from the GLACIMONTIS geodatabase (Lima et al., in review)

(Fig. 2). Further, confusion matrix based scores are calculated to summarise spatial model-data agreement at the LGM and at the model present-day:

$$\text{Confusion matrix score} = \frac{\text{CP} + \text{CA}}{\text{CP} + \text{CA} + \text{U} + \text{O}} \quad (7)$$

where CP is correct presence (both model and validation indicate glacier presence), CA is the correct absence (both model and validation indicate no glacier presence within the simulation domain), U is underestimation (validation indicates ice cover but the model does not), O is overestimation (model indicates ice cover but the validation does not).

However, the correct absence category strongly influences the confusion matrix score as it is calculated over the entire bounding box of each simulation domain. This results in artificially inflated scores, often approaching 100% agreement across all experimental setups, even though the relative validation ranking is preserved. To address this, we developed the Critical Success Index (CSI) score, which excludes correct absences from the calculation and therefore yields more realistic values and more interpretable measures of model–data agreement.

$$\text{CSI} = \frac{\text{CP}}{\text{CP} + \text{U} + \text{O}} \quad (8)$$

2.5.3 Ice volume validation

The simulated ice volume outputs at the modelled present-day are directly compared to the validation dataset of estimated ice volume [Farinotti et al., 2019]. Here, we compute the total ice volume in both the simulated outputs (V_{model}) and the validation dataset ($V_{\text{validation}}$) and, then, calculate the absolute ice volume difference (V_{diff}) between them to score the model-data agreement in each experimental setup:

$$V_{\text{diff}} = |V_{\text{model}} - V_{\text{validation}}| \quad (9)$$

2.5.4 Validation ranking

To analyse and validate each simulation ensemble, the two validation approaches (confusion matrix and volume difference) are combined and the individual simulations are ranked. First, the individual simulations get a confusion matrix validation score for both the LGM and the present-day. Then, the volume difference at present is calculated. This produces three complete ranked lists of simulations, one for each validation method or time. A final ranked list is produced for each ensemble based on the average rank from the three lists. The final ranked list provides a reference for well adapted input parameter ranges for each study area, detailed in Table A1. For each simulation n in an ensemble, the average rank R_n is calculated:

$$R_n = \frac{r_1 + r_2 + r_3 + r_4 + r_5}{5} \quad (10)$$

where r_1 is the rank of the confusion matrix score at LGM, r_2 is the rank of the confusion matrix score at model present-day, r_3 is the CSI score at LGM, r_4 is the rank of the CSI score at model present-day, and r_5 is the rank associated with volume comparison for present day.

2.6 Model evaluation

As multiple parameter and forcing combinations can produce similarly plausible glacier configurations (i.e. equifinality), our model evaluation accounts for ensembles rather than a single best-fit simulation. From the validation ranked list of simulation ensembles, we select the top 20 simulations for each of the simulation domains.

Ensemble ice-cover presence is computed from the selected simulations using a pixel-based methodology. For each grid cell in the simulation domain, we determine whether it is ice-covered across the ensemble and quantify the number of simulations in which coverage occurred. This yields a spatially explicit representation of ice-cover frequency and probability across the acceptable simulation ensemble.

From this spatially explicit field of ice-cover frequency, we calculate percentile ranges and quartiles. Ice-cover frequency is classified into four probability classes corresponding to the proportion of acceptable simulations in which a given grid cell is ice-covered (1–25%, 25–50%, 50–75%, and >75% of simulations). We also extract the 25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles to visualise the interquartile range (IQR) of glacier extent and sensitive to choice of model setup, thereby identifying areas of robust agreement (>75%) from areas where glacier formation occurs only under specific combinations of climate and ice-dynamics parameters (<25%), with intermediate classes (25–75%) indicating regions whose glacier formation varies across acceptable model setups.

3 Results

Across the 14 simulation domains, the IGM glacier model achieves generally good performance (Table 5), with simulation runtime varying from an average of 2.98 hours in the Bale Mountains simulation domain to an average 101.73 hours in the Eastern Cordillera and Merida simulation domain. Across all domains, mean LGM CSI score is 47.79%, in which the Ruwenzori Mountains scores the highest (77.03%) and the Semien Mountains the lowest (24.76%). The CIS score at the model present-day score the highest (100%) when no ice-cover exists (Semien Mountain, Bale Mountains, Arsi Mountains. and Mount Elgon), however the score decreases up to 0% in Sierra Nevada. Table 5 shows the validation scores for each simulation domain. The CSI score is a decent indicator of the spatial agreement between the validation data and the modelled outputs, however, as a validation metric, it is limited by the interaction between model resolution and validation glacier area. This means that present-day glaciers are small enough to be realistic represented by our 500 m model. For instance, in the Ruwenzori Mountains, the Pyrenees, and Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta, present-day glacier area at the validation dataset is under 15km², with individual glacier catchments of 0.44 km² on average. They are represented by few pixels in our model outputs, meaning that even a single pixel of over- or underestimation is enough to exaggerate the CSI score negatively.

To benchmark our validation framework against established modelling studies, we also apply our validation workflow to previously published numerical glacier simulations of LGM mountain glaciers Yan et al. [2018], Mey et al. [2020], Jouvét et al. [2023]. Results show CSI scores of 35.16%, 42.90%, and 71.81% for the benchmark validation, which are consistent with our simulated glacier’s CSI scores (Table 5), indicating a well-performing model for simulating LGM glacier extent.

The CSI score adequately ranks model–data agreement but cannot robustly identify a single best reconstruction, since many parameter-calibration experiments produce similar scores and glacier configurations, and validation datasets carry

Table 5: Best ranked validation simulation result in percentage for the two time steps Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) and present day (PD).

Location	Mean comp. (hours)	Experiments (#)	Validation time step	CSI (%)	Confusion Matrix (%)	Over-estimation (%)	Under-estimation (%)	Correct presence (%)	Correct absence (%)
Santa Marta	15.55	27	LGM	49.48	95.20	12.46	44.35	55.65	98.85
			PD	8.13	99.28	1078.10	4.18	95.82	99.28
Eastern Cordillera and Merida	101.73	27	LGM	37.96	93.82	89.76	27.97	72.03	95.03
			PD	38.11	99.99	69.54	35.39	64.61	99.99
Western and Central Cordilleras	50.77	27	LGM	29.29	94.50	30.97	61.64	38.36	98.05
			PD	31.44	99.99	37.34	56.82	43.18	99.99
Ecuadorian Cordilleras	17.18	27	LGM	41.82	94.11	32.42	44.63	55.37	97.32
			PD	49.35	99.95	49.35	49.35	49.35	99.98
Semien Mountains	4.85	27	LGM	24.76	100.00	98.81	50.78	49.22	99.93
			PD	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
Bale Mountains	2.98	45	LGM	48.94	91.17	60.47	21.47	78.53	92.70
			PD	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00
Ahmar Mountains	3.10	27	LGM	49.10	90.15	45.55	28.53	71.47	6.10
			PD	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00
Mount Elgon	4.04	27	LGM	46.81	98.93	29.48	39.40	60.60	99.54
			PD	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
Mount Kenya and Kilimanjaro	5.01	108	LGM	50.51	96.57	40.89	22.83	65.03	4.75
			PD	1.66	99.77	4755.02	19.39	80.61	99.77
Greater Caucasus	32.52	60	LGM	48.88	94.20	40.59	31.28	68.72	96.43
			PD	26.61	98.48	130.91	37.19	60.95	98.80
California Sierra Nevada	15.53	27	LGM	56.59	90.29	23.98	29.84	70.16	94.72
			PD	0.00	99.96	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00
European Alps	31.27	53	LGM	64.12	80.10	25.39	19.58	80.36	79.69
			PD	30.10	98.58	184.25	14.39	85.55	98.67
The Pyrenees	4.67	81	LGM	64.83	93.28	28.47	16.72	83.28	95.03
			PD	8.16	99.99	23.42	89.92	10.08	100.00
Albertine Rift Ruwenzori	5.26	54	LGM	77.03	98.96	12.62	13.25	86.75	99.47
			PD	3.71	99.70	2496.92	3.58	96.42	99.70

their own uncertainties. In 3 we showcase our model evaluation framework applied to The Greater Caucasus. The top 20 ranked simulations in the simulation ensemble is represented as a heat-map of ice cover probability, showing the ice extent as a likelihood of parameter-calibration setups, rather than a single "best-fit" extent. The scale-bar shows interquartile ranges, where dark-blue represents areas of robust model agreements, where 75% or more simulations, with different parameter-calibration setups, builds ice cover. Meanwhile, light-blue shows areas where only 25% or less simulations build ice-cover, i.e. areas highly sensitive to specific climate settings and ice dynamics parameter combinations. The in-between classes shows the transitional areas from robust agreement to parameter-combination sensitivity.

Overall, both under- and overestimation occur across the domain at the LGM and at the modelled present-day. Nonetheless, the simulated glacier distribution captures the overall configuration and spatial organisation of ice at both time steps. Panels **a** and **b** show the evaluation-framework output overlaid by the GLACIMONTIS validation dataset at the LGM. We see that most simulations underestimate the extent of valley glaciers. At the same time, the model overestimates a larger ice field to the East and South. A broadly similar pattern is evident for the model present-day (panels **c** and **d**), in which over- and underestimation happens simultaneously, but with smaller absolute misalignments. Despite this, the quantitative agreement differs markedly between time slices: the CSI is 48.88% for the LGM but only 26.62% for the model present-day. This contrast illustrates why purely visual validation can be misleading: apparent "reasonable" map-level agreement may mask substantial differences in measured model-data fit, and visual interpretation remains inherently subjective.

Figure 3: Comparison of LGM (a–b) and present day (c–d) simulated extent for the Greater Caucasus, represented as spatial distribution of glacier extent quantiles (25, 50, and 75) from the validated model ensemble. (a) Regional overview of the ranked LGM ensemble compared with the GLACIMONTIS validation dataset. (b) Zoomed-in examples of marginal sectors highlighted in panel a. (c) Regional overview of the ranked model present-day ensemble compared with RGI 7.0 glacier outlines. (d) Corresponding zoomed-in marginal sectors highlighted in panel c. Blue shading indicates how often assemble experiments simulated ice-cover in each pixel classified into percentile ranges; pink indicates the reference validation dataset.

4 Discussion

4.1 Challenges of paleoglacier modelling

Transient paleoglacier modelling across large spatial extents and orbital timescales faces a central constraint: mountain climate forcing is rarely spatially uniform, even within a single named range. Topography imposes strong along-range and cross-range gradients in precipitation and temperature, and these gradients can differ in magnitude and direction between settings. In some regions, glaciers are confined within elongated topographic corridors (e.g., Greater Caucasus, European Alps), whereas in others ice accumulation is restricted to isolated massifs that experience distinct local climates (e.g., Ethiopian Highlands, Eastern Rift Mountains). Proxy evidence underscores the scale of this heterogeneity; for example Rea et al. [2020], reported pronounced spatial variability in precipitation across the European Alps during the Younger Dryas varying from 750 mm/year to 1500 mm/year. Such gradients are difficult to represent with a single forcing scenario, particularly where proxy constraints are sparse. More broadly, orbital-timescale climate variability reflects both external forcing and internal variability, so a unique “best” paleoclimate forcing is unlikely to exist for an entire mountain range Riechers et al. [2022]. Together, these factors imply that a single temperature–precipitation forcing is often an unrealistic assumption for regional paleoglacier simulations.

To reduce mismatches between simplified forcing and true climatic heterogeneity, and thereby improve simulated patterns of ice build-up and extent, we partitioned mountain ranges into multiple simulation domains where needed. This strategy is particularly important in ranges composed of widely separated high-elevation massifs, where applying one shared forcing would inevitably yield realistic behaviour for some massifs and implausible outcomes for others. For the Eastern Rift Mountains, for instance, modelling Mount Elgon, Mount Kenya and Mount Kilimanjaro as one domain (i.e., with identical forcing and ice-dynamic settings) would confound their distinct climatic contexts. Similarly, the Northern Andes and the Ethiopian Highlands show strong internal gradients that are better represented by subdividing the range into smaller, more homogeneous domains (Figure 1). Domain-specific calibration then allows the validation workflow to identify locally appropriate parameter combinations and effective climate forcing values, reducing systematic spatial bias that would otherwise be absorbed into challenging interpretable parameter adjustments.

At the same time, domain partitioning is not universally feasible. Even in geographically compact ranges such as the Pyrenees, spatial climate contrasts can be expressed as systematic misfits: in our simulations, LGM ice cover is larger on the southern side than indicated by the validation dataset, whereas the northern sector is more consistent. Because Pyrenean glaciers were largely connected at the LGM, splitting the domain into independent north–south simulations would break the physical coherence of the ice mass. In this case, we retained a single simulation domain but expanded the calibration space, allowing the validation procedure to identify parameter sets that best balance model–data agreement across the connected system.

A further limitation is that continuous, spatially coherent global paleoclimate reconstructions remain scarce for the Late Pleistocene: long proxy records are typically geographically restricted [see synthesis by Hooghiemstra et al., 2022], global reconstructions often limited in specific time windows [e.g. MARGO Project Members, 2009, Marcott et al., 2013, Kageyama et al., 2021], and available products [e.g. Krapp et al., 2021] are too coarse to resolve the steep gradients that govern mountain glacier mass balance. This scarcity necessitates extensive calibration experiments, but it also means that many temperature–precipitation combinations explored during calibration cannot be independently anchored to a “ground-truth” baseline. Within this constraint, our approach—combining ΔT_{epica} with regionally informed scaling factors derived from multiple proxy sources—provides a pragmatic pathway to impose a continuous, transient temperature signal while retaining regional flexibility. Precipitation remains the more weakly constrained component of the forcing, and improving precipitation priors will be a key avenue for strengthening future large-scale transient mountain glacier reconstructions [Russo et al., 2024, Lleshi et al., 2025].

4.2 Model parameters in IGM

A central practical trade-off in IGM experiments is between computational cost and the fidelity of simulated ice geometry, and our results show that the dominant control is the spatial resolution of the ice-dynamics grid. We initially adopted a 1000 m grid, which is already relatively fine given the continental-scale domains considered here. However, because IGM is trained on much finer spatial scales (200–300 m), stable behaviour at coarser resolution required more aggressive retraining to maintain model adaptability. Increasing the retraining frequency to every time step and the learning rate to $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ substantially increased computational demand and, in early tests, introduced systematic artefacts in the ice-thickness fields. These artefacts were most apparent at valley-glacier termini and along the margins of small ice bodies. For instance, the Bale Mountains (Ethiopian Highlands; LGM extent a $\sim 250 \text{ km}^2$) repeatedly exhibited a one-pixel-thick rim of unrealistically thick ice (up to ~ 400 meter) surrounding interior thicknesses of roughly 100–200 m. Moving to a 500 m grid eliminated the need to deviate from default training settings and yielded more physically plausible thickness patterns, including a smoother tapering of ice thickness toward glacier margins. Although the 500 m

configuration increased runtimes across all domains, the gain in geometric realism, and the removal of resolution-linked artefacts, justified this choice for the transient ensemble experiments presented here.

Finer resolution also imposes hardware constraints. At 500 m, several domains exceed the memory capacity of GPUs with <16 GiB, requiring spatial subdivision into multiple bounding boxes. Where possible, we placed boundaries between hydrological catchments to minimise the risk of truncating flow pathways and to preserve coherent accumulation–ablation structures. This strategy is not universally applicable, however: in strongly interconnected systems such as the European Alps, splitting the domain would cut across contiguous LGM ice masses and compromise the physical validity of the simulation. For that reason, the full European Alps ensemble was run as a single domain on high-memory A100 GPUs on the Sigma2/Saga HPC system.

To keep the global, multi-range transient experiments computationally feasible, we applied several deliberate simplifications. Most importantly, we did not include fully coupled thermodynamics. At the spatial and temporal scales explored here, incorporating thermodynamic evolution would substantially increase runtime and complexity, and it remains secondary to our primary objective: reconstructing time-evolving ice extent. While thermodynamic state can influence margins and flow through its effects on basal conditions and viscosity, explicitly resolving these processes across dozens of large domains and long timescales is currently not tractable within the workflow we target. We therefore prioritised a configuration that can be applied consistently across all mountain regions and that focuses computational resources on robust, spatially explicit ice-extent reconstructions, while identifying the areas of improvements for follow up work.

Isostatic adjustment is a potentially more consequential omitted process for some regions, because bedrock deformation can feed back on surface elevation, hypsometry, and hence mass balance and ice extent. We nonetheless excluded isostasy for two pragmatic reasons. First, it is not yet implemented in IGM in a way that supports efficient GPU parallelisation; in practice, incorporating isostatic adjustment would require repeated CPU-side calculations at each (or many) time steps, markedly slowing the transient ensembles. Second, physically credible isostasy requires additional region-specific parameters that themselves require calibration, an expansion in parameter space that is beyond the scope of this study. For the largest domains (notably the European Alps), and potentially for medium-sized systems when treated as fully connected ice masses (e.g., the Northern Andes), neglecting isostatic adjustment could affect reconstructed extents and should be addressed in follow-up work. At the global multi-range scale targeted here, however, consistent, well-constrained isostatic estimates remain unevenly available or still under active development, so we exclude this process while recognising it as a clear priority for next-generation transient paleoglacier reconstructions.

4.3 Validation

Although several tools have been developed to quantitatively validate modelled outputs to geomorphic evidence [Napieralski et al., 2006, Li et al., 2007, 2008, Ely et al., 2021, Archer et al., 2023] and several quantitative validation workflows have been applied to validate and evaluate the spatial agreement between modelled and validation datasets [e.g. Becker et al., 2016, Candaş et al., 2020, Köse et al., 2022, Leger et al., 2025, Lleshi et al., 2025], validation of paleoglacier modelling outputs has heavily relied on simple visual comparisons [e.g. Hostetler and Clark, 2000, Kull et al., 2003, Sternai et al., 2013, Xu et al., 2014, Višnjević et al., 2020, Jiang et al., 2022, Quirk et al., 2024, Zhang et al., 2024]. Where quantitative validation is performed, evaluation strategies often differ substantially between studies in terms of the methodological approaches, selected metrics, temporal reference, geomorphic evidence, and validation targets, and commonly still rely on implicit, study-specific judgement to determine which model–data agreements are considered the most acceptable [Gandy et al., 2024].

The reliance on visual comparison reflects several persistent challenges inherent to paleoglacier model validation. In many mountain regions, geomorphic evidence are limited by substantial spatial gaps of mapped ice landforms and research coverage. Where glacial landforms are consistently mapped, geomorphic evidence is often fragmentary, unevenly preserved and spatially discontinuous, their spatial accuracy vary widely, and their digital accessibility are highly inconsistent. Additionally, glacial landforms carries centennial to millennial-scale chronological uncertainties and potential overprinting of multiple advances, as chronology dating is method-dependent, thus, limiting precise temporal alignment with transient model outputs. Together with strong parameter uncertainty and equifinality in glacier models these factors have historically favoured qualitative, visual assessment of model–data agreement.

A key distinction in paleoglacier model validation lies between the use of spatially continuous, geomorphically reconstructed glacier extents and validation based on geomorphic evidence (e.g., moraine crests, trimlines, erratic boulders). Although field-based geomorphic evidence provides invaluable constraints on past glacier limits and is frequently used directly in model validation [e.g. Hostetler and Clark, 2000, Plummer and Phillips, 2003, Kessler et al., 2006, O’Donnell, 2010, Kaufmann and Romanov, 2012, Xu et al., 2014, Leonard et al., 2014, Mey et al., 2020, Jiang et al., 2022, Stansell et al., 2022, Yan et al., 2023, Doughty et al., 2023, Quirk et al., 2024, Zhang et al., 2024], point- and line-based landforms offer only sparse spatial information and are often difficult to compare directly with gridded model

output, particularly at regional scales of hundreds to thousands-of-metre resolution. Small positional uncertainties in glacial landform mapping or modelled ice margins can translate into large apparent misfits when distance-based metrics are applied, even when overall glacier geometry is well reproduced.

In contrast, geomorphically-based reconstructions integrate multiple lines of geomorphic evidence and provide spatially explicit glacier extents that are more directly comparable to modelled ice masks, allowing model–data agreement and disagreement to be evaluated across the full glaciated domain rather than at a limited number of locations. Zekollari et al. [2022] note that glacier model behaviour can be assessed through comparison with alternative representations of glacier evolution, a practice that has been adopted in several studies using geomorphic glacier reconstructions as independent constraints on modelled glacier extent [e.g. Golledge et al., 2012, Becker et al., 2016, 2017, Seguinot et al., 2018, Cohen et al., 2018, Višnjević et al., 2020, Imhof, 2021, Yan et al., 2022, Jouvet et al., 2023, Castillo-Llarena et al., 2024, Çiner et al., 2024, Leger et al., 2025, Lleshi et al., 2025].

The application of geomorphic glacier reconstructions for paleoglacier model validation has long been limited by fragmented data sources that are inconsistently accessible, unevenly distributed across regions, or represent synthesis efforts that have not been systematically updated. Here, the GLACIMONTIS geodatabase (Lima et al. in review) addresses these limitations by compiling published geomorphic reconstructions into a single, openly accessible, and spatially explicit global dataset. Nevertheless, geomorphically based reconstructions in GLACIMONTIS still carry inherent uncertainty, including variable completeness, schematic or abstract representations derived from limited geomorphic evidence, positional inaccuracies introduced during analogue-to-digital conversion, and spatial resolutions that may differ from those of numerical model outputs. In addition, paleoglacier reconstructions frequently integrate glacier advances over extended time intervals.

These uncertainties motivate validation approaches that treat reconstructed glacier extents as uncertain spatial constraints rather than exact ground truth. Our probabilistic, equifinality-aware validation framework provides a robust and scalable alternative to traditional model evaluation. By evaluating ice-cover as a probability derived from the ensemble of acceptable simulations, rather than selecting a single best-fit model realisation, our approach explicitly acknowledges parameter non-uniqueness and uncertainty inherent to paleoglacier modelling calibration and validation. Summarising ice-cover probabilistic occurrence using interquartile ranges allows spatial patterns of robust agreement and persistent uncertainty to be distinguished, highlighting regions where glacier extent is consistently supported by the model ensemble versus areas that are sensitive to parameter choices or limited observational constraints. Thus, our framework is well suited to spatially explicit, grid-based glacier models and accommodates the heterogeneous quality, coverage, and temporal uncertainty of geomorphic validation data, while avoiding subjective selection of individual simulations. As such, it provides a transparent and quantitative means of evaluating model–data agreement and represents a pragmatic step toward more reproducible validation of transient paleoglacier simulations.

Finally, we found that IGM can develop non-physical flow behaviour in narrow valleys and along glacier margins when run at coarser spatial resolution (e.g. 1 km), unless the training/retraining settings are tuned for each simulation—an adjustment that increases computational cost. By moving to 500 m resolution, we obtained markedly more realistic ice geometries without extensive fine-tuning. Nevertheless, because IGM was originally trained on substantially finer grids, its full potential is likely realised at higher spatial resolutions than those explored here.

5 Conclusion

Our study shows that orbital-timescale, high-resolution mountain glacier modelling is now tractable at global scale, and that IGM is a genuinely enabling step-change for the community: it combines physically grounded ice dynamics with GPU efficiency in a way that makes transient ensembles across 130 kyr feasible across multiple mountain regions. We address several of the core barriers identified in the introduction: (i) uncertain initialisation/forcing, (ii) patchy paleoclimate constraints, (iii) poorly constrained ice-dynamic parametrisations, (iv) uneven validation data, and (v) the lack of standardised, reproducible evaluation under equifinality. By combining a 10 kyr spin-up, regionally scaled climate forcing, systematic calibration (617 experiments), and joint areal + volumetric benchmarking against GLACIMONTIS (LGM; Lima et al. in review) and present-day glacier extent, we show that IGM can reproduce realistic ice geometries and transient evolution across diverse mountain settings at 500 m resolution, while also providing a clear diagnostic of where performance degrades and which domains require finer resolution, better forcing priors, or tighter regional calibration.

A second key conclusion is methodological: we make equifinality an explicit feature rather than a hidden nuisance, and turn it into an interpretable spatial product. Instead of selecting a single “best” run, we introduce a spatially explicit, probabilistic evaluation workflow (confusion-matrix/CSI ranking + ensemble percentiles) that maps where glacier presence is robust (>75% agreement across acceptable simulations) versus parameter-sensitive (<25%), thereby formalising uncertainty in a transparent and reproducible way. This matters because transient glacier histories are

foundational boundary conditions for broader mountain and alpine research and confidence in those boundary conditions depends on systematic model–data testing. Just as importantly, our modelling framework is portable and expandable: the pipelines are designed to scale to additional mountain ranges through modular domain definition, regionally tuned calibration ensembles, and efficient execution on local GPUs or HPC. In combination, these advances position IGM not only as a powerful tool for global paleoglacier reconstruction, but as a practical foundation for a next generation of open, comparable, and continually updatable mountain glacier simulations.

6 Appendix A

Table A1: Key varied parameters and best fit simulation parameter values for the simulation ensemble

Location	Varied Parameter	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Rank 4	Rank 5	Range
Santa Marta	f_{regional}	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
	P_{LGM}	1.5	1.7	1.9	1.5	1.9	1.5–1.9
	Sliding Coefficient	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225	0.09	0.0225–0.0900
	DDF	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.1–1.3
Eastern Cordillera and Merida	f_{regional}	0.74	0.74	0.74	0.74	0.74	0.74
	P_{LGM}	1.75	1.5	1.5	2	1.75	1.5–2.0
	Sliding Coefficient	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225–0.0900
	DDF	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.1–1.3
Western and Central Cordillera	f_{regional}	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65
	P_{LGM}	1.5	1.5	1.75	1.5	2.0	1.5–2.0
	Sliding Coefficient	0.045	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225–0.0900
	DDF	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.2–1.5
Ecuadorian Cordilleras	f_{regional}	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
	P_{LGM}	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.1–0.8
	Sliding Coefficient	0.0225	0.0225	0.0450	0.0200	0.0225	0.0200–0.0450
	DDF	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.2	1.3	1.2–1.4
Semien Mountains	f_{regional}	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65
	P_{LGM}	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6–0.8
	Sliding Coefficient	0.0450	0.0450	0.0900	0.0450	0.0900	0.0450–0.1350
	DDF	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.1	1.2	1.1–1.3
Arsi Mountains	f_{regional}	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6
	P_{LGM}	1.0	1.0	1.1	0.9	0.9	0.9–1.1
	Sliding Coefficient	0.0900	0.0900	0.0450	0.0900	0.0450	0.0225–0.0900
	DDF	1.4	1.3	1.4	1.3	1.3	1.1–1.4
Bale Mountains	f_{regional}	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45
	P_{LGM}	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3–0.5
	Sliding Coefficient	0.0450	0.0450	0.090	0.090	0.045	0.0225–0.0900
	DDF	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.3–1.5
Mount Elgon	f_{regional}	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65
	P_{LGM}	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5–0.9
	Sliding Coefficient	0.0250	0.0900	0.0900	0.0450	0.0250	0.0250–0.0900
	DDF	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.2–1.5
Mount Kenya and Kilimanjaro	f_{regional}	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
	P_{LGM}	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.4	0.3–0.5
	Sliding Coefficient	0.4500	0.0900	0.0150	0.1800	0.0150	0.0100–0.4500
	DDF	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.4	1.3–1.5
Greater Caucasus	f_{regional}	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
	P_{LGM}	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.3–0.7
	Sliding Coefficient	0.0450	0.0900	0.0900	0.0450	0.0250	0.0200–0.1800
	DDF	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.4	1.2–1.7
California Sierra Nevada	f_{regional}	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
	P_{LGM}	1.8	1.8	1.8	2.0	2.0	1.8–2.1
	Sliding Coefficient	0.0225	0.0450	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225–0.0900
	DDF	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.8	0.9	0.8–1.0
European Alps	f_{regional}	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
	P_{LGM}	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.4–0.6
	Sliding Coefficient	0.0225	0.0900	0.0450	0.0225	0.4500	0.0225–0.4500
	DDF	1.4	1.6	1.8	1.2	1.6	1.2–1.9
The Pyrenees	f_{regional}	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1
	P_{LGM}	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.2–0.4
	Sliding Coefficient	0.450	0.090	0.4500	0.1800	0.0900	0.0225–0.4500
	DDF	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.2	1.3	0.9–1.5
Ruwenzori Mountains	f_{regional}	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
	P_{LGM}	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.5–0.7
	Sliding Coefficient	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225	0.0225–0.0900
	DDF	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.3	1.3–1.5

Author contribution

S.B. ran the glacier simulations. A.C.L. synthesised climate scenarios for glacier simulations, contributed to model set up, and result analyses. D.C. contributed to model set up and result analysis. A.T.W. designed the initial workflow for running IGM with paleo climate data. E.S.R. calculated the original spatial lapse rates and the regional scaling factor values based on regional climate proxies. R.P.P. contributed to setting up the model on recent hardware. S.G.A.F. led the project and manuscript development, supervised the conceptual and methodological approaches, and obtained funding. S.B. and A.C.L., developed the first manuscript draft with critical contributions from S.G.A.F. and D.C., with all authors contributing to all manuscript versions and key elements throughout the project.

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